

MAIN TECHNIQUES FOR GETTING STARTED WRITING PROCESS

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Abstract

The article describes school textbooks and added some new activities which we considered suitable for teaching and improving students' writing skills. The main methods for compiling our work are the method of analysis and the method of research. In our work, we analyzed school textbooks and added some new activities which we considered suitable for teaching and improving students' writing skills.

Key words: writing skill, school textbooks, communicative competence, task-oriented activities

Annotatsiya

Maqolada maktab darsliklari haqida so'z boradi va biz o'quvchilarning yozish ko'nikmalarini o'rgatish va yaxshilash uchun mos deb hisoblagan bir qancha yangi mashg'ulotlar qo'shiladi. Bizning ishimizni tuzishning asosiy usullari tahlil usuli va tadqiqot usulidir. Biz o'z ishimizda maktab darsliklarini tahlil qildik va o'quvchilarning yozish ko'nikmalarini o'rgatish va oshirish uchun mos deb bilgan bir qancha yangi tadbirlarni qo'shdik.

Kalit so'zlar: yozish mahorati, maktab darsliklari, kommunikativ kompetentsiya, vazifaga yo'naltirilgan faoliyat

Аннотация

В статье рассматриваются школьные учебники и добавляется ряд новых видов деятельности, которые мы считаем подходящими для обучения и совершенствования навыков письма учащихся. Основными методами организации нашей работы являются аналитический метод и метод исследования. В нашей работе мы проанализировали школьные учебники и добавили ряд новых видов деятельности, которые мы считаем подходящими для обучения и совершенствования навыков письма учащихся.

Ключевые слова: навыки письма, школьные учебники, коммуникативная компетентность, ориентированные на задачу виды

In recent years language researchers and practitioners have shifted their focus from developing individual linguistic skills to the use of language to achieve the speaker's objectives. This new area of focus, known as communicative competence, leads language teachers to seek task-oriented activities that engage their students in creative language use. In the process of learning English as a foreign language, writing is considered as one of the most essential skills. In addition to being a communicative skill of vital importance, it is a skill which enables the learner to plan and rethink the communication process. Therefore, teaching writing skills should be taught gradually starting from instrumental skill to content-based writing. Teaching writing should be started from beginning level. Most school textbooks are focused on teaching writing separately without integration of other skills. In other words, our qualification work pursues as its major aim to help foreign students improve their writing skills with the integration of other skills from the beginning level. The significance of our work can be proved that we tried to find optional methods of improving writing skills from the beginning level and we applied them in practice.

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In our research we used the ideas of Uzbek, Russian and foreign methodologies who worked in the sphere of foreign language teaching methodology and language learning. We addressed to works of J. Jalolov, G. Rogova, Spack.R, G. L. Rico, J. Arnold, M. Boden and others for theoretical part of our work. In practical part of our work we appealed to school textbooks "Prepare" 7 and 8. This theme has been worked out by many scientists and researchers before but from the point of analyzing Uzbek school textbooks and creating a series of writing tasks in those textbooks hasn't been done yet. Also, we consider the idea of approbating new writing materials on English language lessons during our pedagogical practice is also one part of the novelty of our work. The present work might find a good way of implying in the following spheres:

1. In High Schools and scientific circles of language teaching methodology it can be successfully used by teachers and philologists as modern material for writing research works dealing with improving writing skills.
2. It can be used by teachers of schools, lyceums and colleges by teachers of English as a practical manual for teaching writing.
3. It can be useful for everyone who wants to enlarge his/her knowledge in English.

The growth of composition studies as a discipline with its own independent body of research (apart from, say, literary studies or linguistic studies) has enormously influenced the formal training of English. For EFL teachers to be able to provide courses which assist their students in learning to produce academic prose, their training should be no less than other skills.

It has been the major aim of our research work to emphasize the fact that teaching writing skills is particularly important at the initial stage of language learning since it helps students establish a good basis in learning other skills such as reading, speaking and listening. We worked out a series of activities for improving students' writing skills and combined them with the tasks given in the textbooks. When we analyzed the textbook activities, we found that most of them teach writing in phrases or sentences. The activities which we applied teach students mostly creative writing and make them be more motivated in writing.

We tried to vary writing tasks, make them more creative and we came to a conclusion that students love writing because of interesting tasks. We both benefit: students because learning to write is enjoyable for them, teachers benefit because they feel the need to improvise, to make writing more attractive to students and think of and look for more creative tasks. In order to be able to select and use appropriate procedures and materials, as well as assess their learners needs and progress, teachers need to be clear regarding the desirable outcomes of a writing programme and the processes involved in good writing.

In order to help EFL learners become more effective writers, we need to make a crucial distinction between language accuracy and writing skills. That is, a learner may be able to write sentences which are satisfactory for his/her level in terms of grammar, syntax and vocabulary and still be unable to produce an effective text. Of course, in most cases learners will have problems in both areas (language and writing skills). Therefore, it is crucial for us to be able to look beneath the layer of language problems to discover writing problems. This leads us to another important distinction, the one between grammar/vocabulary development and writing skills development. We need to remember that language input/practice alone cannot result in the development of writing skills. Special activities in writing lessons are necessary, in which learners are guided to become aware of all the elements of good writing, supported with information and examples, provided with opportunities for practice, and given focused feedback on their performance. We can also plan lessons

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which integrate work on language with work on writing skills. In such cases, it is important for us to be clear about the aims/focus of different stages in the lesson. In order to be able to select and use appropriate procedures and materials, as well as assess their learners needs and progress, teachers need to be clear regarding the desirable outcomes of a writing programme and the processes involved in good writing.

In conclusion, if teachers are eager to be more creative and innovative, they can find various activities to improve writing skills but they should take into consideration the following facts:

- 1) to create tasks in accordance with students level of English and interest
- 2) to teach writing starting from skill building exercises to process based
- 3) to get started form pre-writing techniques to proof reading
- 4) to let students do peer checking
- 5) to combine reading and writing tasks
- 6) to use techniques mentioned above

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